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Environmental, economic, and social impacts of methane cracking for hydrogen production: A comprehensive review

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ABSTRACT

Methane cracking (MC) is emerging as a low-carbon hydrogen production technology. This review conducts a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of 46 studies examining the sustainability of MC process. The review employs Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Cost (LCC), Techno-Economic Analysis (TEA), and Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) methodologies. The findings reveal that LCOH for MC technologies ranges from 0.9 to 6.6 \$/kg H₂, at the same time, GHG emissions span 0.8–14.5 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂, depending on the specific reactor configurations, plant geographical locations, and carbon revenues. These results indicate that MC can be competitive with steam methane reforming with carbon capture and electrolysis under certain conditions. However, the review identifies significant research gaps, including limited comprehensive LCA studies, a lack of social impact assessments, insufficient environmental impact analysis of molten media catalysts and particulate matter formation in MC processes, as well as insufficient analysis of the potential of biomethane cracking.

Abbreviations

AEL	Alkaline Electrolysis
ATR	Autothermal reforming technology
AWARE	Available water remaining
BECCS	Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage
CAPEX	Capital expenditure
CB	Carbon black
CECPI	Chemical engineering plant cost index
CF	Carbon footprint
CG	Carbon gasification
CNT	Carbon nanotube
DCF	Discount cash flow
EAF	Electric arc furnace
EF	Environmental footprint
FU	Functional unit
GHG	Green house gas
GWP	Global warming potential
IRR	Internal rate of return
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCC	Life cycle cost
LCDME	Levelized cost of dimethyl ether

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LCMeOH	Levelized cost of methanol
LCOC	Levelized cost of carbon
LCOE	Levelized cost of energy
LCOH	Levelized cost of hydrogen
LCOP	Levelized cost of product
MC	Methane cracking
MM	Molten metal
NG	Natural gas
NGL	Natural gas liquified
NTP	Non thermal plasma
OPEX	Operational expenditure
PEMEL	Proton exchange membrane electrolysis
RHER	Regenerative non-catalytic heat exchanger reactor
ROI	Return on investment
SLCA	Social life cycle assessment
SMR	Steam methane reforming
SMR CCS	Steam methane reforming with carbon capture
SOEL	Solid oxide electrolysis
TAC	Total annualised cost
TCD	Thermal catalytic decomposition
TD	Thermal decomposition

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TEA	Technoeconomic analysis
TP	Thermal plasma
TRACI	Tool for reduction and assessment of chemicals and other environmental impacts

1. Introduction

Hydrogen (H₂) plays a pivotal role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) and achieving the objectives of the Paris Agreement [1]. Its application as a feedstock or energy vector could be widely applied in transport (heavy road, maritime and aviation) and heavy industry sectors such as steel and cement, fertiliser production and power generation [2]. According to the IEA NZE Scenario, the H₂ production capacity of 95 Mt/year needs to increase to 150 Mt/year by 2030 and 430 Mt/year by 2050 to significantly contribute to cumulative emissions reduction in the energy sector [1]. Of this hydrogen, 97.6 % should be targeted as low carbon emissions hydrogen, reaching yet 46.7 % within 2030 [1]. Today, H₂ production is still associated with processes that emit GHG, contributing over 900 million tons of CO₂ annually [3]. Steam methane reforming (SMR) and coal gasification (CG) are the primary H₂ production routes emitting 10–13 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂ and 22–26 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂, respectively [3]. Applying carbon capture and storage (CCS) technology to the SMR and CG processes can reduce GHG emissions to 1.5–6.2 kgCO₂eq/kgH₂ and 2.6–6.3 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂, respectively, with levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) rising from 1.0 to 3.0 \$/kgH₂ to 1.5–3.6 \$/kgH₂ [3]. Despite its potential, CCS technology faces challenges: current projects produce only around 10 Mt per year of low-carbon H₂, far below the 17 Mt CUS needed in 2030 per the NZE Scenario [3]. Additionally, only 6 % of announced projects are under construction, mainly due to long construction times developing and permitting new storage resources, low development of circular economy and upcycling of CO₂ emissions, lack of certification schemes (emissions reductions, guarantees of origin) [2,3]. Water electrolysis can potentially reduce fossil fuel dependence with total GHG emissions ranging from 0.5 to 24 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂, depending on the electricity mix [3]. The main obstacles to water electrolysis implementation include technological challenges, high costs (ranging from 3.4 to 12 \$/kgH₂), water scarcity, geopolitics and power competition over access to strategic locations and natural resources of critical material [3–6]. In 2023, H₂'s low carbon emissions production reached only 1 Mt (0.7 % of global production), mainly attributed to fossil fuel plants with CCS and water electrolysis, which account for 0.07 % of the total annual production [3]. In this scenario, the methane cracking (MC) technology for H₂ production is emerging as a bridge technology, potentially filling the gap between high-emissions traditional fossil fuel production routes, the costly electrolysis and the difficult implementation of SMR CCS. The MC process directly

decomposes methane into H₂ and solid carbon. The avoided direct CO₂ production, together with the use of low carbon electricity resources or the H₂ self-sustained process, has the potential to reduce the GHG emissions compared to SMR and facilitate the transition to the low carbon H₂. Monolith is the first commercial plant producing turquoise H₂ and valuable carbon, with expansion planned for 2025 [7]. Along with Monolith, other MC projects are achieving high TRL, indicating growing interest in the technology. However, the economic, environmental, and social impacts of MC processes to produce H₂ must be thoroughly evaluated to fully understand their sustainability and alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goals [8]. This paper aims at providing more insights regarding the impacts associated with MC technologies through an extensive literature review process. This literature review process will be focused on answering the following questions:

- What is the methodological approach applied in the life cycle and techno-economic analysis to assess the environmental, economic, and social impact of MC technologies?
- What is the environmental, economic and social impact of the

MC technologies?

- Are MC technologies competitive with electrolysis and SMR CCS?
- What are the next strategies to address the sustainability of MC technologies?

The document is organised as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the low carbon emissions hydrogen technologies, including MC processes, and their classification into Conventional Gas, Molten Media, and Plasma Systems. Section 3 outlines the methodology used to select studies for the review. Section 4 presents and discusses the results of the selected papers, analysing methodological approaches and results for economic (4.1), environmental (4.2), and social (4.3) impact. These sections also address a comprehensive analysis of the LCOH and GHG emissions to discuss the competitiveness of MC with SMR CCS and electrolysis and the potential role of biomethane cracking as a bioenergy capture and storage (BECCS) solution (4.4). Finally, Section 5 concludes the review of MC's environmental, economic, and social impacts and provides recommendations for further research.

2. Low carbon emissions hydrogen technologies

The uptake of hydrogen economy for net zero emissions future is based on the production of low carbon emissions hydrogen. The technologies with higher TRL for low carbon emissions hydrogen production include water electrolysis, reforming with carbon capture, methane cracking, biomass and non-biological waste gasification and pyrolysis [3,9]. The technological aspects of each process are described in the following paragraphs and summarised in Fig. 1.

2.1. Electrolysis

Water splitting via water electrolysis is an electrochemical reaction, as described by the reaction 1:

It takes place in electrolysis, which consists of a cathode and an anode immersed in an electrolyte in which the electrical current flows and provides the necessary energy for the water-splitting reaction. Water electrolysis projects dominate among the announced hydrogen production projects: more than 70 % of low-emission hydrogen production in 2030 could come from electrolysis [3]. The main electrolysis technologies are alkaline-based (AEL), proton exchange membrane (PEMEL), and solid oxide electrolysis (SOEL).

AEL and PEMEL are mature technologies, both reaching commercial operation in a relevant environment (TRL 9), and representing the 60 % and 30 % of the electrolyser installed capacity in 2023, respectively [3]. However, based on projects' announcements this share is expected to change in the coming years, with PEMEL gaining market share over AEL thanks to the improved PEMEL's suitability for the operation with a fluctuating power supply. SOEL is hot temperature water electrolysis [9, 10]. It is the least mature among the electrolysis technologies, but its readiness level is gradually increasing, supported by its application in a range of settings, from chemical production to steelmaking, where waste heat can be valorised to increase the process efficiency [9]. IEA considers it to be at TRL 8, first of a kind commercial deployment stage [3].

2.2. Reforming with carbon capture and storage

Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) is the dominant industrial method

Fig. 1. Description of low carbon emission hydrogen technologies.

for producing hydrogen today, favored for its efficiency and established infrastructure [9]. It is a catalytic conversion of methane and steam to hydrogen and carbon dioxide as described by the reaction 2:

The method entails three steps: generation of H₂/CO (ratio 3:1), Water-Gas Shift and methanation or gas purification. In the first process step, methane and water react to form gaseous hydrogen and carbon monoxide (syngas). Then during the Water-Gas Shift, carbon monoxide reacts with water to form hydrogen and carbon dioxide. Subsequently, the pressure swing adsorbent step is used to separate hydrogen and CO₂.

Retrofitting carbon capture technology on existing SMR units is possible, but it reduces the efficiency of the process and increases the hydrogen cost. Carbon capture units must be installed to capture CO₂ from the flue gas from the SMR process to achieve the highest CO₂ capture rate at around 90 % or higher. In the existing SMRs plants, the carbon capture technology is applied only in the process gas stream, achieving a carbon capture rate of around 60 % [9]. New opportunities are arising from the capturing CO₂ emissions focus on autothermal reforming technology (ATR). ATR of natural gas combines steam methane reforming and partial oxidation. When using carbon capture equipment, it does not have to be installed twice (on process and flue gases), thus simplifying the process, making it more efficient, and lowering its costs. Projects planning to use auto thermal reforming with carbon capture aim to achieve at least 94 % carbon capture rates. While being a choice for a large majority of future low-carbon hydrogen projects, ATR with carbon capture does not yet have a significant commercial operational experience, reaching TRL 5–6 (large prototype/full prototype) [9].

2.3. Biomass and non-biological waste gasification and pyrolysis

The biomass and non-biological gasification and/or pyrolysis processes are divided into 4 steps: 1) biowaste pretreatment, 2) gasification and/or pyrolysis, 3) Water Gas Shift, 4) Gas purification. Gasification is a thermochemical process in which the feedstock is converted into hydrogen syngas and by-products at high temperature (700–1100 °C) and in presence of oxidants (air, O₂). In pyrolysis, the thermochemical reaction happens in the absence of oxygen. The by-products of the reactions depend on the feedstock and the technology, and can include ash, biochar, and tar [9]. When the plant is retrofitted with CCS technology and biomass feedstock is used (BECCS), it is possible to reach carbon negative emissions. However, the emissions intensity of bioenergy-based routes will strongly depend on upstream emissions of the feedstock supply chain [11]. The current TRL of biomass and non-biological waste gasification and pyrolysis for hydrogen production is at TRL 5–6 according to the IEA [3]. However, there are also technologies at TRL level 8 and 9 [9]. The main limit to the technology

development is the risk of insufficient feedstock and the high cost of feedstock transportation.

2.4. Methane cracking

Methane cracking, also known as methane pyrolysis or methane decomposition, is a thermochemical process that splits methane into hydrogen and solid carbon, such as shown in the reaction 3:

The reaction is endothermic with an enthalpy of 74.52 kJ/mol [12]. However, the implementation of the technology has been limited by the high temperature of 1300–1600 °C. Three main technological strategies have been focused [12]: 1) Conventional gas system, 2) Molten Media system (MM) and 3) Plasma system. The classification is illustrated in Fig. 2 where the advantages and disadvantages of each technology are described. The systems reach TRL between 6 and 8 [9].

2.4.1. Conventional gas

In conventional gas systems, the MC reaction occurs in a tubular fixed-bed or fluidized-bed reactor. The high temperature inside the reactor (1300–1600 °C) causes methane thermal decomposition (TD) [13]. To lower the process temperature (500–1000 °C), metal (Ni or Fe) or carbon-based catalysts can be introduced, in which case it is known as thermal catalytic decomposition (TCD) [12,13]. However, the use of these type of catalysts is a challenge due to rapid deactivation caused by carbon deposition on their surface. Catalyst reactivation through gasification can be performed, but this process results in CO₂ production.

Over the past few decades, several industrial projects have been developed, leading to significant advancements in the TRL. Hazer [14] and Huntsman Nanocomp [15] companies have announced plans to build commercialisation plants in 2025 and 2026, respectively [16]. Meanwhile, the Finnish Hycamite planned the pilot plan in 2024 [17].

2.4.2. Molten media

In the Molten Media system, molten metals or salts inside the reactor serve a multifaceted role. Firstly, they act as an efficient heat transfer medium, optimising the thermal dynamics of the reaction. Secondly, simplify the separation since they rise to the surface, facilitating an easy natural extraction. Lastly, depending on the specific material,

the liquid can serve as a catalyst. Various molten media have been proposed, including Gallium, Tin, Tellurium, metal alloys like Nickel and Bismuth (Ni_{0.27}Bi_{0.73}) or alkali-halide salts, such as NaCl, NaBr, KCl, and KBr [18]. These last are interesting thanks to low cost, high-temperature stability, and non-toxicity. The major barriers to this technology include the need for further separation of carbon from the molten liquid material, impurities in the carbon byproduct. This technology has reached its highest TRL with the C-zero molten salt bubble

Fig. 2. Methane cracking technologies description.

reactor [19]. Currently, a commercial plant of 6 tons/day is planned for 2025 [16].

2.4.3. Plasma

In plasma reactor technologies, energy is provided by plasma, which is typically generated with electricity. Electrons are created, accelerated, and collided with methane molecules to dissociate them. Two different kinds of plasma technologies are under development: 1) The thermal plasma or “hot” plasma process reaches a temperature higher than >1000 K. In this case, the plasma temperature is homogeneously distributed, achieving a chemical equilibrium of all species; 2) In a Non Thermal or “cold” plasma process, the ionised gas is in thermodynamic non-equilibrium, with an average temperature of less than 1000 K [20]. However, small species like neutrons and electrons reach temperatures up to 10,000 K [12]. Cold plasma has the advantage of lower energy consumption, but the process’s conversion efficiencies are inferior to those of hot plasma technology. Thermal plasma technology has successfully reached a commercial scale. The Monolith plant, situated in the USA, boasts a production capacity of 13 tons per day for both H₂ and carbon black [7]. The upcoming phase is targeted at commercial hydrogen generation for ammonia production, aiming

to reach a capacity of 200,000 tons of H₂ per year by 2026 [21]. H-Quest company plans to establish a commercial plant with a capacity of 1 ton per day utilising microwave plasma technology [9,22]. On the other hand, Hiiroic and Modern Hydrogen companies are on schedule to launch a pilot plant between 2024 and 2025 [17]. Lastly, Levidian, Plenesys, Graforce, and Sakowin have slated the launch of their demonstration plants by 2024 [16,23–26].

3. Methodology

This review focuses on selecting scientific papers related to the economic, environmental, and social performance of MC technologies for H₂ production from a life cycle and techno-economic perspective. The life cycle is a worldwide recognised methodology that evaluates the environmental, economic, and social impacts of a product or process along its life phases. The life cycle assessment (LCA) focuses on analysing the environmental impact. It is a holistic, comprehensive and international standardised methodology supported by the ISO 14040–14044: 2006 [27,28]. It includes aspects for environmental impact assessment along the life cycle stages of a product or service, suggesting various environmental metrics. When the analysis is focused on assessing GHG emissions, it is referred to as life cycle GHG emissions or carbon footprint (CF) analysis, which is supported by the specific regulation ISO 14067 [29].

The LCC is an extension of the LCA methodology focused on economic evaluation where all costs associated with the life cycle are analysed and covered by any one or more of the actors in the product life cycle (supplier, producer, user/consumer, end-of-life-actor) [30]. The code of practice for environmental life-cycle costing is the LCC guideline [31]. The high data detail required by LCC makes it difficult to apply to low TRL (1–5). This is due to the uncertainty of the final design and technology characteristics, and the unavailability of data at a large scale [32,33]. The techno-economic analysis (TEA) includes the LCC approach, adapting it for low-TRL technologies with economic competitiveness from an investor’s perspective. Besides, TEA is a widely used tool by both academic and industrial researchers, the US national laboratories such as the National Energy Technology Laboratory and international research collaboration groups such as the Global Carbon Initiative, the International CCU Assessment Harmonization Group to

evaluate economic performance of new technologies [34]. The TEA ensures compatibility with the life cycle methodology by following the steps indicated by ISO 14040–14044 standards [27,28]. Additionally, the ISO 14076 Eco-Technoeconomic Analyses: Principles, Requirements, and Guidelines is currently under development [35]. Finally, the Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) evaluates an organisation's or product's social impact through its life phases. The SLCA methodology is based on 'Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations' developed by UNEP and SETAC [36]. The authors' decision to adopt life cycle methodologies and techno-economic analysis is founded on their thoroughness, adaptability to low TRL processes, international standardisation, and extensive application in European legislation [37] and hydrogen sustainability certification [38].

The methodology described in Fig. 3 is applied to conduct the bibliometric review and identify relevant studies. The research was performed in SCOPUS [39].

To this end, the following Boolean string was used to combine keywords with operators like AND, OR, and NOT to refine and improve search results: TITLE-ABS-KEY (“Life cycle assessment” OR “Life cycle cost” OR “Life cycle costing” OR “Life cycle greenhouse gas emissions” OR “carbon footprint” OR “Techno-economic” OR “social life cycle assessment” AND (“methane cracking AND hydrogen” OR “methane pyrolysis AND hydrogen” OR “turquoise hydrogen”)) AND PUBYEAR >2000 AND PUBYEAR < 2024”). This search string was designed to find documents containing terms related to life cycle assessment (LCA), carbon footprint (CF), life cycle cost (LCC), techno-economic analysis (TEA), and social life cycle assessment (SLCA) in combination with critical phrases covering methane cracking hydrogen production technologies such as “turquoise hydrogen,” “methane pyrolysis hydrogen,” or “methane cracking hydrogen”. The review includes these terms in the documents' title, abstract, or keywords. The search was limited to articles and reviews published between 2000 and 2024 and written in English. The period selection aligns with the dissemination of the mentioned methodologies in scientific literature, while the language constraint is based on the authors' comprehension. The search, conducted on August 7, 2024, yielded 142 documents. The documents underwent a screening process using the following inclusion criteria: 1) The primary products of the MC process must be hydrogen and carbon; 2) The documents must include an economic, environmental, or social impact evaluation. During the first screening phase, which involved reading titles and abstracts, 73 documents were excluded. The criteria for exclusion were grouped into four main clusters: 1) Papers lacking any economic, environmental, or social evaluation; 2) Papers not including the MC process; 3) Papers involving the direct cracking of

solid biomass feedstock, leading to differing product outcomes (mainly heavy oil) and reactor requirement; 4) Papers with unavailable abstracts. In the selection phase, the full texts of the remaining documents were reviewed, leading to the exclusion of 23 studies. The exclusion criteria from the screening phase were reiterated, with the addition of complete text unavailability leading to the exclusion of 5 more documents. Ultimately, 46 documents were selected for review.

4. Results and discussion

The selected documents are presented in Table 1, with a detailed description of the process, methodological approach, and results. The economic analysis section indicates the methodological approach (TEA or LCC), economic indicators, carbon selling price and results. The environmental section reports the methodological approach and results with FU, system boundaries, multifunctionality, environmental indicators, and methods. When not specified differently, all the impacts are attributed to the H₂. When the information is not directly detachable from the document, the abbreviation N/A is reported. The first analysis of the selected documents focuses on the publication years. As illustrated in Fig. 4 interest in MC's economic, environmental, and social sustainability has grown in the last four years, with the publication rate sparking from 1 to 2 documents per year from 2009 to 2020 to 7 to 12 papers from 2021 to 2024. The increment observed is aligned with the raised industrial interest in MC technology and the increased attention of the scientific community on the sustainability challenge.

The second step of the review focuses on analysing the selected studies according to the MC technologies analysed (Conventional gas, MM and Plasma systems). The results are presented in Fig. 5a. The number of publications evaluating Conventional Gas is 22, with 18 studies focusing on catalytic process (TCD) [40–57] and 4 on TD [40,41, 47,57]. The MM process is analysed in 18 selected documents [10,40, 58–73], while only 7 and 1 investigate Thermal Plasma (TP) [11,40,47, 67,71,74,75] and Non Thermal Plasma (NTP) [76] reactors, respectively. The publication trend captured by the review does not reflect industrial development [16]. Although plasma technologies have been the subject of fewer studies than conventional gas and MM, they are the only technologies with a commercially operative plant and the highest number of advanced TRL projects. This discrepancy is particularly evident for NTP, with only 1 publication identified.

In the third step, the documents are classified based on the sustainability pillars they address (economic, environmental, and social) and their specific methodologies (Fig. 5b). The methodologies classifications are TEA and LCC for the economic evaluations, and Life cycle CO₂ emissions, Life cycle GHG emissions and LCA for environmental

Fig. 3. Bibliometric review methodology.

Table 1

Selected documents of the bibliometric review include a process description, an economic and environmental analysis methodological approach, and results.

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
Keipi et al. ^b [57]	1. TD 2. TD 3. TCD 4. TD with Regenerative heat exchanger reactor (RHER)	1. NG combustion 2. Electrical heating 3. Carbon combustion 4. Electrical heating	N/A	TEA	Cost of net electricity production (\$/MWh)	540 \$/ton (500 EUR/ton)	LCOE \$/MWh (EUR/MWh) 1. 197 (183) 2. 275 (255) 3. 233 (216) 4. 278 (257)	Carbon selling ^a price (0–3000) \$/ton carbon LCOE 350–0 (EUR/MWh)	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions	FU: 1 MWh Gate-to-gate	CO ₂ emissions	tCO ₂ /MWh 1.0.55 2.0.83 3.0.48 4.0.85	
Parkinson et al. [60]	MM catalytic iron	1. Electrical heating 2. Electrical heating (with catalyst) 3. NG combustion 4. H ₂ combustion	N/A	TEA	LCOH	200 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1. 1.74 2. 1.62 3. 1.61 4. 1.58	N/A	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions	FU: Ton H ₂ Gate-to-gate	CO ₂ emissions	tCO ₂ /ton H ₂ 1. 3.1 2. 2.7 3. 1.5 4. 0	
Parkinson et al. [61]	MM Catalyst Ni-Bi alloy	NG combustion	U.S. Gulf coast	TEA	LCOH	150 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1.39	Carbon selling price ^a (0–500) \$/ton LCOH 0.4–1.8 \$/kg H ₂ CO ₂ charge (50–100) \$/tCO ₂ LCOH 1.39–1.8 \$/kg H ₂ Capital cost (±20 %) LCOH 1.26–1.43 \$/kg H ₂ NG price (2–6 GJ) ^a LCOH 0.9–2 \$/kg H ₂					
Parkinson et al. [78]	MC process from literature review	N/A	N/A	LCC	LCOH	N/A	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1.76	Carbon selling price (10–150) \$/ton for \$4 GJ/NG LCOH 1.36–1.79 \$/kg H ₂	Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate	GWP Method N/A	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) 6.1 (09 % methane emissions)	0.6–1.4 % (central 0.9 %) fugitive methane emissions GWP 4.2–9.14 (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂)
Timmerberg et al. ^b [12]	1. TP 2. TP 3.MM 4.TD	1. Electrical heating from combined cycle power plants 2. Electrical	Global NG supply chain	TEA	LCOH	0 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) ^a 1.1.7 2. 2.21 3. 1.51 4.1.57	Carbon selling price ^a (0–550) \$/ton 1..LCOH 1.7–0 \$/kg H ₂ Carbon selling	Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate, including manufacturing.	GWP Method IPCC AR5	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) ^a 1.1.2.5 2. 6.5 3.11.5 4.14.5	Natural gas supply chain emissions (3–50 g CO ₂ eq/MJ) ^a GWP

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
		heating from renewable power supply 3. NG combustion 4. NG combustion						price (0–700 \$/ton) 2.LCOH 2.21–0 \$/kg H ₂ Carbon selling price ^a (0–500 \$/ton) 3. LCOH 1.51–0 \$/kg H ₂ 4.LCOH 1.57–0 \$/kg H ₂					1. 5–20 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ 2. 1–11 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ 3. 4–18 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ 4. 5–22.4 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂
Wald et al. [62]	MM	Electrical heating	United States	TEA	LCOH	150 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1.75	Carbon disposal (10 \$/ton) LCOH 2.23 \$/kg H ₂ Carbon credit from low carbon fuel standard program LCOH 0.39 \$/kg H ₂ Other sensitivity analysis: IIR, lang facto, carbon revenues, electricity price, NG price, lifetime.	LCA	FU: 1 kg H ₂ 30 bar Cradle-to-gate.	Human health, ecosystem quality and resource depletion at the endpoint level Method RECIPE 2016:	Human health (DALYs/kg H ₂) ^a <1 Ecosystem quality (species/kg H ₂) ^a <0.2 Resource depletion (USD2019/kgH ₂) ^a 1.5–1.6 0.90	Country sensitivity analysis Denmark, Sweden, Norway Germany
Al-Qahtani et al. [59]	MM catalytic Ni-Bi alloy, heat with NG	NG combustion	United States	LCC with externalities, including decommissioning	LCOH	0 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) MC: 1.87 4.92 with environmental externalities						
Bhaskar A [73]	MM (electric heat) with tin integrated in steel shaft furnace (SF) is connected to an electric arc furnace (EAF) for	Electrical heating	EU 28	TEA	LCOP, IIR	200 \$/ton	LCOP 631 (\$/t)	Local and global sensitivity analysis for NPV and IRR	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions	FU: 1 ton of liquid steel (tIs) Cradle- to-gate	CO ₂ emissions		

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
Cheon et al. [41]	steel production fed by MC H ₂ 1. TD 2. TCD 3. TD with carbon gasification and water gas shift reaction 4. TCD with carbon gasification water gas shift reaction	NG and H ₂ combustion	N/A	TEA	LCOH	500 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1. 2.14 2. 3.66 3. 3.53 4. 3.82	Sensitivity analysis (±20 %) MP reactor price 1. 12.1 % 2. 10.9 % 3. 6 % 4. 3.09 % Carbon selling price 1. 19.1 % 2. 11.1 %	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions	FU: 1 ton H ₂ Gate-to-gate	CO ₂ emissions	N/A	
Kerscher et al. ^b [79]	NTP	1a. Electrical power from GE grid 1b Electrical power from RE 2. Self-sustaining H ₂	Germany	TEA	LCOH	108 \$/ton 100 EUR/kg H ₂	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1 2.75 (2.55) 2. 5.4 (5) In brackets (EUR/kg H ₂)	Carbon selling price (-60-100 \$/ton) 1.LCOH 2.55-3.02 (\$/kg H ₂) 2. LCOH 6.08-5.00 (\$/kg H ₂) CAPEX accelerator (1.5-5.k\$) 1. LCOH 1.46-2.55 \$/kg H ₂ 2.LCOH 2.21-5 \$/kg H ₂ Other sensitive analysis: NG price, CO ₂ certificate price	Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate with plant manufacturing,	GWP Method IPCC AR 5	GWP kgCO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ 1a 1.9 renewable 1b 6.4 GE electrical mix 2. 4-5	
Leal Pérez B. J. et al. ^b [63]	MM (liquid gallium)	1a CB combustion 1b CB combustion with CCS 2. H ₂ combustion 3a. NG combustion 3b. NG combustion with CCS 4. Electric heat	N/A	TEA	LCOH	320 \$/ton (296 EUR/ton)	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1a 3.18 (2.94) 1b. 3.19 (2.95) 2. 4.35 (4.03) 3a. 3.81 (3.53) 3b. 3.76 (3.47) 4 3.41 (3.16) (EUR/kg H ₂)	NG price (0.19-0.39 \$/kg NG) If NG < 0.194 MM LCOH < \$/kg NG 0.286 (\$/kg H ₂) Carbon sale price (200-400 EUR/ton) With 400 EUR/ton all MMs <3.36 (EUR/kg H ₂) Molten metal life time (5-0.5	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Gate-to-gate	CO ₂ emissions	kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂ 1a. 5.26 1b 0.45 with CCS 2. 1.46 3a 6.16 3b. 0.56 with CCS 4. 1.01	

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
Riley J et al. [42]	TCD iron catalyst	1.NG combustion 2.H ₂ combustion	N/A	TEA	Breakeven selling price H ₂	0–10 \$/kg	LCOH \$/kg H ₂ 1. 0–2.94 (carbon selling sensitivity analysis) 500 \$/ton carbon, 20 % of the carbon sold 2.6 2. 0–3.1 (carbon selling sensitivity analysis) 500 \$/ton carbon, 20 % of the carbon sold 2.8	years 1a,1b,3a,3b,4 increase of 0.5–0.7 EUR/kg H ₂ 2 increase 2.12 EUR/kg H ₂ Carbon tax (0 \$-100 \$tCO ₂) 2 and 3 not competitive with SMR and SMR CCS for all the range	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Gate-to-gate	CO ₂ emissions	kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂ 1. 2 2. 0	Sensitivity analysis: carbon sale price, catalyst recovery Catalyst activity 1. Catalyst cost (1–8 \$/kg), carbon selling price (0–0.5 \$/kg C) and catalyst activity 4.9e-5 gcarbon/gcatalyst-sec. LCOH 4.02–1.20 \$/kg H ₂
Lumbers B et al. [43]	Iron mine decarbonisation TCD with iron catalyst	NG combustion	Australia	TEA	LCOH	10 \$/kg (graphitic) with only 10 % recover	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1.45 Medium (25–50 Mt) LCOH 1,40 \$/kg H ₂ Large (<50 Mt) LCOH 1.45 \$/kg H ₂	Iron mine scale Small (<25 Mt) LCOH 1,39 (\$/kg H ₂) Medium (25–50 Mt) LCOH 1,40 \$/kg H ₂ Large (<50 Mt) LCOH 1.45 \$/kg H ₂	Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: Annual iron mine activity Cradle-to-gate (including H ₂ storage)	GWP Method IPCC AR 5	GWP MtCO ₂ eq/year 0.425	Iron mine scale Small (<25 Mt) 0.16MtCO ₂ eq/year Medium (25–50 Mt) 0.299 MtCO ₂ eq/year Large (<50 Mt) 0.425 MtCO ₂ eq/year
Oni et al. ^c [80]	1.TCD (Fe catalyst) 2.TCD CCS (Fe catalyst)	NG combustion	Canada, Alberta province	TEA	LCOH	55 \$/ton 74 CAD/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1. 1.57 2. 1.89 CAD/kg H ₂ 1.2.12 2. 2.55	Sensitivity analysis with Morris method	Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate (NG, electricity and direct emissions)	GWP Method N/A	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) 1. 4.89 2. 4.54	

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
Pruvost F et al. ^b [64]	Molten media catalyst KCl/MnCl ₂	NG combustion	Europe	TEA	LCOC		LCOC (\$/ton) 216–432 (200–400 EUR/ton)	NG price 2–10 EUR/GJ ^a LCOC (0–500 \$/ton) Electricity price (30–90 \$/MWh) LCOC 200–400 (\$/ton) Discounts rate 3–13 % LCOC 270–370 (\$/ton)					
Swartbooi et al. [44]	TCD from biomethane	Purge gas combustion	South Africa	TEA Scenarios with and without carbon selling	LCOH	1670 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 14.4 no carbon selling 8.88 with carbon selling						
Ali et al. [45]	RHER [57]	NG combustion	Europe	TEA Scenarios with and without carbon selling and carbon tax	LCOH TAC	500 \$/t	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 3.73 with carbon tax/ without byproduct sales 3.42 without carbon tax or byproduct sales 1.93 without carbon tax/ with byproduct sales 2.24 with carbon tax and byproduct sale		LCA	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Gate-to-gate Including plant construction and operations, NG transportation and electricity.	GWP, water footprint, IMPACT 2002+ indicators Method IPCC AR4 AWARE	GWP (kg CO ₂ e/kg H ₂) 6.92 (IMPACT 2002+) 8.87 (IPCC AR4) Water footprint (kg water/kg H ₂) 5.15	
He Y et al. [58]	Molten metal with chemical looping combustion	NG combustion	N/A	TEA	LCOH	300 \$/t	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1.12	NG price 3–7 \$/GJ LCOH 0.55–1.70 \$/kg H ₂ Carbon taxes (0–160 \$/t) LCOH 1.12–0.6 \$/kg H ₂					
Li Y et al. [46]	H ₂ -burning power plant integrated with an onsite hydrogen production unit TCD 1. Ni	NG combustion	N/A	TEA	LCOE	1 and 2. 12550 \$/ton (CNT) 3.CB 1365 \$/ton	Net-LCOE: \$/MWh 1. 2184 2. –123 3. 118	Sensitivity analysis conversion rate, bypass ratio, carbon selling price, catalyst cost	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions	FU: 1 MWhe Gate-to-gate	CO ₂ emissions	kgCO ₂ /MWhe 0.51	

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
Al Ghafri et al. [47]	2. Fe 3. Carbon TD TCD Thermal plasma	1. TD electrical heating 2. TCD electrical heat 3. TCD NG combustion 4. Thermal plasma	NG extraction Australia, H ₂ production Japan	TEA	LCOH	0 \$/ton	LCOH: \$/kg H ₂ 1. 4.00 2. 3.70 3. 2.60 4. 6.60		Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate	GWP Method N/A	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) 1.6.9 2.6.4 3.5.8 4.1.1	
	Ostadi et al. [65]	H ₂ integration for methanol production from: 1. Biomass 2. Municipal organic waste MM catalytic Ni-Bi alloy,	NG combustion	N/A	TEA	LCMeOH	100 \$/ton	LCMeOH (\$/MeOH) 1. 433 2. 404	Local sensitivity analysis ^a Price of carbon, cost of NG, cost of biomass, cost of electricity, Purchased equipment, number of operating hours, discount rate Lifetime				
Mahabir et al. [48]	Methanol production through CO ₂ hydrogenation TCD	NG combustion	US state of Louisiana	TEA	TAC	N/A	TAC (\$/tonne MeOH) 383	Market sensitivities 4–5 %	LCA	FU: 1 ton MeOH Cradle-to-gate (excluded catalyst)	Midpoint and endpoint by RECIPE 2016 (Method)	Human health (DALYs/tonn MeOH) ^a 55–60 Ecosystem quality (species/tonn MeOH) ^a 8–10 Resource depletion (USD2013/tonn MeOH) ^a 34–35	
Kim et al. [66]	MM (Cu _{0.45} Bi _{0.55}) along with NaBr.	Purge gas combustion in oxy-fuel combustor	N/A	TEA	LCOH	No selling	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1.34	Carbon tax 0 to 150 \$/tCO ₂ ^a LCOH 1.33–1.35 (\$/kg H ₂) NG price 3 to 10 \$/MMBTU LCOH 0.8–1.5 (\$/kg H ₂) Carbon selling price \$/ton 1.34–0.9	Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle to gate	GWP Method N/A	GWP (kgCO ₂ eq/kGH ₂) 13.22 –0.31 calculating the CO ₂ capture from solid carbon and the oxy-fuel combustor	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
Salas et al. [11]	TP with carbon black graphitisation 1. NGL into liquid fuel 2. NGL into chemical 3. NGL into chemicals with electrification	Electricity	United States (Texas)						Life cycle GHG emissions Scenarios: a grid mix b wind renewable	FU: 1 metric tonnes t/H ₂ , 1 MJ NG, 1 metric tonnes of graphite Cradle-to-gate Multifunctional approach: Economic allocation	GWP Method: IPCC AR 6	GWP (metric tonnes CO ₂ eq/metric tonnes H ₂) 1a. 3.67, 1b 0.71 2a 3.67, 2b 0.71 3a 3.80, 3b 0.78	
Mondal et al. [49]	TCD with carbon gasification	NG combustion	N/A	TEA	LCOH		Estimated production cost (\$/MT H ₂) 9	Methane conversion efficiency: 39.8 % Estimated production cost 948 \$/MT H ₂ Methane conversion efficiency: 50 % Estimated production cost 899 \$/MT H ₂	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions	FU: ton H ₂ Gate-to-gate	CO ₂ emissions	6.93 kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂	Methane conversion efficiency: 39.8 % 6.87 kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂ Methane conversion efficiency: 39.8 % 6.93 kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂
Okeke et al. [50]	TCD	1a NG air combustion with CCS 1b NG air combustion 2a. NG O ₂ combustion with CCS 2a NG O ₂ combustion 3a CB air combustion with CCS 3b CB air combustion 4a CB O ₂ combustion 4b CB O ₂ combustion with CCS	Canada	TEA	LCOH	300 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1a 2.43, 1b.1.64, 2a 1.95, 2b 1.90 3a 2.83, 3b 1.08, 4a 1.71, 4b 1.45	Natural gas 0.9–14.4 \$/GJ LCOH 0.72–6 \$/kg H ₂ Carbon selling price (–0.30–1 \$/kg) LCOH 1a. 3.31 to –0.48 \$/kg H ₂ LCOH 1b 2.69 to –1.83 (\$/kg H ₂) LCOH 2a 2.94 to –1.53 (\$/kg H ₂) LCOH 2b 2.99 to –1.58 (\$/kg H ₂) With and without carbon tax LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1a 2.43–3.10 1b.1.64–2.31 2a 1.95–2.61 2b 1.90–2.56 3a 2.83–4.01 3b 1.08–2.02	LCA FU: 1 kg H ₂	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate Multifunctional approach: Energy allocation	GWP, respiratory effects, and fossil fuel depletion Method: TRACI v2.1 IPCC AR5	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) ^b 1a 2.1, 1b 3.6 (7) 2a 1.8, 2b 3.6 (7) 3a 4.6, 3b 11.4 (13.6) 4a 2.4 4b 11.6 (13.6) (In brackets values without energy allocation) Respiratory effects: From 0.8 to 1.5 gPM2.5eq/kgH ₂ Fossil fuel depletion: Up to 6.2 MJ surplus per kg H ₂	Upstream natural gas emission factor from 0.2 to 1.1 kgCO ₂ eq/kg NG TCD with CC design (1a,2a,3a,4a) GWP 1.2–11.1 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ with allocation TCD without CC (1b,2b,3b,4b) GWP 2.5–13.7 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ with allocation

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
Tabat et al. [67]	Mobile microwave catalytic (MM Ni-Br) methane pyrolysis carbon is gasified to generate heat and produce H ₂ through WGS The CO ₂ is then used for methanation with H ₂		North America	TEA	NPV, LCOH ROI		LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1.31	4a 1.71–2.79 4b 1.45–2.41 Sensitivity analysis ±20 % Labour cost Utility cost Feedstock cost equipment purchase cost Data are not provided in the paper					
Angikath et al. [68]	MM 1. Ni-Bi 2. Ga 3. KCl MnCl ₂	Electrical heat	Saudi Arabia	TEA	LCOC LCOH	No carbon selling for LCOH	LCOC (\$/ton CO ₂) 1. 581 2. 833 3. 506 With hydrogen selling price 1.728 \$/kg H ₂ LCOH 1. 0.9–1.18 (\$/kg H ₂)	LCOC is close to zero or even negative, with natural gas costs of \$132/ton and \$198/ton for electricity costs of \$48 and \$24 respectively					
Rezaei et al. [69]	DME plant based on the reformation of CO ₂ using H ₂ produced from CH ₄ decomposition in a molten Cu-Bi alloy	Purge gas combustion	N/A	TEA	LCDME	700\$/ton	LCDME 608 \$/ton DME	Carbon selling price (0–1000 \$/ton) 1208–349 \$/ton DME	Life cycle CO ₂ emissions Scenarios: 1. NG 4000 km pipeline 2. Remote NG plant near DME	FU: MJ DME Cradle-to- gate	CO ₂ emissions	gCO ₂ /MJ DME 1. 17.9 2. 0.4	
Razmi et al. [70]	Molten salt with heliostat solar field with high-temperature thermal energy storage unit 1. Renewable energy 2 Grid mix	High-temperature heliostat solar field	Canada and United States	TEA	LCOH	300 \$/ton	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1. 1.93	Carbon selling price 0–400 \$/ton With US incentives LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1.2.83–0.95 2.2.93–1.23 NG cost (2–10 \$/GJ) without incentives LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 2.1.05–2.81 System life span Off-peak electricity price					

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
								Cost reduction renewable energy infrastructure (%)					
								2. 20 % reduction to <1 \$/kg H ₂ with US incentives					
								2. 50 % reduction to <1 \$/kg H ₂ with US incentives					
Shokrollahi et al. [71]	MM Ni-Bi [60] TP	1. NG combustion 2. H ₂ combustion 3. Electrical heat 4.TP	Canada (Alberta, British Columbia, Ontario; Quebec)	TEA	LCOH	200 \$/ton Base scenario 2 for the production capacity of 20,000 kg/day	LCOH (\$/kg H ₂) 1. 2.92 2. 3.32 3. 4.56 4. 4.89	Scenario 1-3 NG (2–6\$/GJ) Electricity price (0.02–0.1) Carbon selling (400-0\$/ton) 1. 1.15–4.70 2. 1.18–5.47 3. 2.51–6.60 4. 2.56–7.22	Life cycle GHG emissions Scenarios: Electricity and NG supply chain	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate	GWP Method: TRACI 2.1	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) 1.2.58 2 0.0.76 3. 1.21 4. 1.64	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) Range values in 4 different Canadian provinces 1.2.6–4.9 2 0.0.8–3.4 3. 1.2–9.5 4. 1.64–13.5
Patel et al. [51]	TDM Keipi [57]	NG combustion	Finland						Life cycle GHG emissions Scenarios: 1. NG pipeline from Russia 2. LNG USA	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate	GWP ₁₀₀ GWP ₂₀ Method: EF	GWP ₁₀₀ (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) 1. 6.1 2. 8.3	
Diab et al. [74]	TP- Monolith [7]	Electrical heat	United States						Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ , 1 kg graphite, 1 kg coke Cradle-to-gate, including BoP and carbon pelletising Multifunctional approaches: 1. Economic allocation 2. Mass allocation 3. Mass allocation with biomethane feedstock 4. No allocation	GWP Method: IPCC AR6	GWP: (kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂) 1. 0.91 2. 1.16 3. –5.22 4. 4.85	

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
Lawson et al. [75]	TP- Monolith [7] Feedstock: 1. NG 2. Ethane 3. Biodiesel	Electrical heat	United States						Life cycle GHG emissions	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle-to-gate, including BoP and carbon pelletising. Multifunctional approach: Mass allocation	GWP Method: IPCC AR6	GWP: (kg CO ₂ /kg H ₂) 1. 0.91 2. 1.36 3. 1.41 (0.52 including biogenic carbon credits)	
Postel et al. [72]	MM (liquid tin)	H ₂ combustion	Germany						LCA	FU: 1 kg H ₂ at 1 atm Cradle-to-gate with BoP	GWP, fossil depletion impact, metal depletion impact, and particulate matter Method: ReCiPe 2008	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) 3.9 Fossil depletion impact (kg oil-eq/kg H ₂) 7.0 Metal depletion impact (kg Fe-eq/kg H ₂) 0.5 Particulate matter (kg PM10-eq/kg H ₂) 3.3E-3	Scenario 1. Experimental scale 900 °C 9.5 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ 2. Experimental scale 1100 °C 5.5 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ 3. Industrial scale 3.9 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ 4. Stoichiometric limit 1.9 kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂ GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) EU context: 1. 1.62–9.03 2. 4.68–10.38 3. 3.11–8.17 4. 1.40–11.7
Hermesmann et al. [10]	Molten metal (liquid tin) [72]	1. NG combustion 2. H ₂ combustion 3. CB combustion 4. Electrical heat	Germany						LCA Scenarios: Selected european countries NG and electricity mix	FU: 1 kg H ₂ Cradle -to-gate Multifunctional approach: System expansion for carbon black production	EF indicators	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/kg H ₂) 1. 6.45 (0.83) 2. 3.94 (–1.85) 3. 7.65 (3.78) 4. 9.91 (4.28) (In brackets results with system expansion)	
Dufour et al. [54]	Catalytic decomposition 50 % methane conversion efficiency Comparison with fossil fuel process with CCS.	NG combustion	Europe						LCA	FU: 1 Nm ³ H ₂ Cradle-to-gate with BoP	Single score, GWP, fossil energy use (only energy consumption) Method: IMPACT2002, ecoindicator 95, IPCC AR4,	GWP (kg CO ₂ e/kg H ₂) ^d 2.80 (0.25 kg CO ₂ eq/Nm ³ H ₂) Single score (10 ³ Pt/Nm ³ H ₂) < SMR CCS Fossil energy use (MJ/Nm ³ H ₂) < SMR CCS	
Dufour et al. [53]	Catalytic decomposition 1.50 % CH ₄	NG combustion	Europe						LCA	FU: 1 Nm ³ of H ₂ (99.99 % purity)	Single score Method:	GWP (kg CO ₂ e/kg H ₂) ^d 1.2.9 (0.26	

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
	conversion 2. 100 % CH ₄ conversion											kgCO ₂ eq/Nm ₃ H ₂) 2. 1.77 (0.16 kgCO ₂ eq/Nm ₃ H ₂) Single score (mPt/Nm ³ H ₂) 1. < SMR 2 > SMR	
Dufour et al. [55]	Catalytic decomposition 1.50 % CH ₄ conversion 2.50 % CH ₄ with solar concentration system	NG combustion	Europe						LCA	FU: 1 Nm ³ of H ₂ (99.99 % purity). Cradle-to-gate with BoP	GWP, cumulative energy demand, cumulative exergy demand Method: IPCC AR 4	GWP (kg CO ₂ e/kg H ₂) ^d 1. 2.89 (0.26 kgCO ₂ eq/Nm ₃ H ₂) 2. N/A Fossil energy use (MJ//Nm ³ H ₂) 1 and 2 < SMR CCS. Exergy efficiency 1 and 2 < SMR CCS. Renewability 1 < SMR CCS 2 > SMR CCS	
Dufour et al. [52]	1.TCD metal (Fe) 2.TCD (carbocenus 70 % conversion eff) 3. TCD (carbocenus, 96 % conversion eff)	NG combustion	Europe						LCA	FU: 1 Nm ³ of H ₂ (99.99 % purity). Cradle-to-gate with BoP	Greenhouse effect, energy ratio, single score. Method: Ecoindicator 95	GWP (kg CO ₂ e/kg H ₂) 1 2.89 (0.26 kgCO ₂ eq/Nm ₃ H ₂) 2. 2.44 (0.22 kgCO ₂ eq/Nm ₃ H ₂) 3. 1.77 (0.16 kgCO ₂ eq/Nm ₃ H ₂) Single score (mPt/Nm ³ H ₂) 3 < 2 < 1 H ₂ energy/ input fossil energy ratio SMR < 3 < 2 < 1	
Mohamed et al. [56]	Ammonia production with H ₂ was produced by TCD, employing a	Solar collector	Norway						LCA	FU: 1 kg NH ₃ Cradle-to-gate with plant manufacturing	GWP, human toxicity, terrestrial acidification, fine particulate	GWP (kg CO ₂ e/kg NH ₃) 0.724 (0.616) (In bracket results with CO ₂ e/kg NH ₃)	Cracking temperature (600–900 °C) 0.722–0.724 kg

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Table 1 (continued)

Source	Process			Economic analysis				Environmental analysis					
	Technology description	Heat generation	Geographical location	Methodology	Economic Indicators	Carbon selling price	Results	Sensitivity analysis	Methodology	FU, system boundaries and multifunctional approach	Indicators and method	Results	Sensitivity analysis
	concentrated solar tower.										matter formation potential, metal depletion. Method: RECIPE 2016	system expansion) Human toxicity-cancer (kg1,4-DBeq/kg NH ₃) 0.009 Terrestrial acidification (kg SO ₂ eq/kg NH ₃) 1.629E-03 Fine particulate matter formation (kg PM _{2.5} eq/kg NH ₃) 6.41E-04 Metal depletion (kg Cueq/kg NH ₃) 5.35E-03 Photochemical Ozone formation, human health (kg NOx eq/kg NH ₃) 0.6078	Operation years (5–50) 0.860–0.714 kg CO _{2e} /kg NH ₃
Chan et al. [81]				TEA review									
Nemitallah et al. [82]				TEA review									
Mohideen et al. [83]				TEA review									
Osman et al. [84]									LCA review				
Maniscalco et al. [85]									LCA review				

^a Exact values are not reported in the original papers and they are extracted from the figures.

^b Values are reported in EUR and converted in USD using 2023 annual exchange rate of 1.08 [86].

^c Values are reported in CAD and converted in USD using 2023 annual exchange rate of 0.74 [87].

^d GHG emissions are reported in kgCO_{2eq}/Nm₃ H₂ and converted kg CO_{2eq}/kgH₂ using the H₂ density value of 0.0899 kg/m³ [89].

Fig. 4. Ratio of publications by year.

analysis. The necessity to include the category Life cycle CO₂ emissions has been made necessary, considering the high number of publications solely focus on CO₂ molecule emissions, excluding the other GHG as required by the Carbon footprint regulation [77]. The results are presented in Fig. 5b. The review identified 33 publications examining MC's economic aspects [40–50,57–71,73,78–83] and 33 studies focused on environmental performance [10,11,40,42,43,45–57,59,60,63,66,69,71–73,75,78–80,84,85]. In contrast, none of the selected documents analysed the social impact. The selected studies focus principally on the H₂ production phase, while a reduced number includes its final use in products such as methanol [48,65], dimethyl ether [69], steel [73], iron mine activity [43] or electricity production [46,57].

4.1. Economic aspects

In the analysis of methodologies for economic assessment, TEA stands out as the primary tool for evaluating the economic performance of MC technologies, with 31 publications identified, including 3 reviews [40–50,57,58,60–71,73,79–83]. On the other hand, only 2 studies adopted the LCC specifically for comparison purposes [59,78]. The economic analysis typically involves calculating capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operational expenditures (OPEX) using a discount cash flow (DCF) approach, with the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) being the most common indicator. For H₂ used in fuel production, indicators such as the levelized cost of methanol (LCMeOH) [48,65] and levelized cost dimethyl ether (LCDME) [69] are employed. The levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) [46,57] is used considering energy production. Some studies also utilise levelized cost of carbon (LCOC) [64], levelized cost of products (LCOP) [73], internal rate of return (IRR) and return on investment (ROI) [61,67,73] and total annualised cost (TAC) [48]. Of the TEAs identified, 18 include the calculation of GHG missions in terms of CO₂ eq [40,42,43,45–50,57,60,63,66,69,71,73,79,80]. The economic analysis reviewed includes scenarios analysis focused on the carbon

selling price, carbon tax, LNG and electricity prices, discount rates, CAPEX, and plant capacity. For each document reviewed, the LCOH of the MC base scenario is identified, excluding feedstocks other than NG. All the LCOHs are reported in Table 1, as reported as identified in the original paper. Values reported in EUR and Canadian dollars are converted into USD using the 2023 annual exchange rate of 1.08 EUR [86] and 0.74 CAD [87], respectively. Original and converted results are both reported in Table 1. The homogenization of the values according to the inflation rate is not performed and is out of the scope of this study. The LCOH conversion to the 2023 USD should be performed as reported by Parkinson et al., identifying the CAPEX cost and actualising it using the CECPI [78]. The use of the inflation rate, average consumer prices, therefore, is not methodologically appropriate for this scope. Riley et al.'s [42] case base scenario is not defined. In this case, the values are extrapolated from the carbon revenues sensitivity analysis at a carbon selling price of 500 \$/ton carbon, considering 20 % of the carbon sold of the total produced. When the specific values are not reported in the original paper, they are extrapolated from the figures [40]. LCOHs' base case scenarios are statistically elaborated in Fig. 6. The reported cost intervals for Conventional Gas are \$1.08–4.00, with median values of 2.24 \$/kgH₂ and Q1 and Q3 values of 1.68 and 3.50 \$/kgH₂, respectively. Okeke et al. reported the lowest price [50]. In this study, the reactor heat is supplied directly by the combustion of the produced carbon. Including CCS technology, the cost increased by 2.83 \$/kgH₂, while the NG combustion scenario accounted for 1.45 \$/kg H₂. The higher cost of 4.00 \$/kg H₂ is calculated by Al-Ghafri et al., where the heat is supplied by an electric arc furnace (EAF) [47]. This study includes the expenses of carbon black transport and storage. For the MM technology, the identified LCOH interval is 0.9–4.56 \$/kg H₂, with median values of 1.80 \$/kgH₂ and Q1 and Q3, respectively, of 1.51 and 3.34 \$/kgH₂. Angikath et al. report the lowest LCOH at 0.9 \$/kgH₂ for a catalytic molten Ni-Bi alloy system. The competitive H₂ price is

Fig. 6. Statistical analysis of LCOH for the base scenario of Conventional Gas, MM, and Plasma systems as identified in the selected documents and reported in Table 1.

Fig. 5. Number of publications according to a) MC technology and b) sustainability pillars.

calculated in Saudi Arabia with a favourable NG and electricity cost of 60 \$/kg and \$48/MWh [68]. Parkinson et al. calculated an LCOH of \$1.39 per kg H₂ for a catalytic molten Ni-Bi alloy process, with heat supplied by NG combustion [61]. The cost of 4.35 per kg H₂ is identified by Perez et al. [47] for the Gallium molten metal system with an H₂ fire heat supply source. The molten media material has a not negligible role in the economic impact assessment, with gallium molten metal being the most expensive among the options [68]. Shokrollahi et al. report the highest LCOH of 4.56 \$/kgH₂ in the Canadian region when EAF heats the system [71], in line with the cost calculated by Al-Ghafri et al. [47]. Compared to the Conventional Gas and MM systems, plasma processes are characterised by the higher LCOH range of 1.73–6.60 \$/kgH₂, with median values of 3.82 \$/kgH₂ and Q1 and Q3, respectively, of 2.09 and 6.00 \$/kgH₂. The highest production cost is related to the higher electricity consumption. In the identified range, the lower costs of 1.73 and 2.21 \$/kg H₂ are calculated by Timmerberg et al. for gas power plants and renewable sources, respectively [12]. In this case, the lower costs are obtained considering the electricity price of 33.6 €/MWh and 41.7 €/MWh from the gas power plant and the renewable system, respectively [88]. The NTP system's cost is reported at 2.75 \$/kg H₂ [79]. The lower energy consumption decreases the LCOH, while the high cost of the electron accelerator limits its further reduction [79].

The sensitivity analysis of the selected studies revealed that the economic profitability of MC technologies is closely tied to carbon revenue [60]. Physical and chemical characterisations are essential to defining the potential market and examining the presence of impurities and their impact on carbon applicability, conductivity, catalyst effect, and resistance. Table 2 presents the allotropes of carbon, their prices, potential applications and annual market sizes.

Currently, the carbon market is significantly smaller than the H₂ market: producing 6.5 annual MMT (million metric tonnes) of H₂ through the MC process is sufficient to saturate the carbon demand.

Therefore, identifying new carbon sectors is vital to enhance the profitability of MC technology [13]. Carbon's use as carbon black in cement, asphalt, steel, and water treatment sectors is proposed. Shifting focus to the production of graphite, graphene, and nanotubes could open new markets requiring high-performance materials, such as batteries, fuel cells, solar cells, and the automotive and aerospace industries. Adopting high-purity needle coke could also mitigate the environmental impact of carbon extraction, transportation, and production processes [61].

4.2. Environmental aspects

The environmental analysis of the MC technologies, as shown in Fig. 5 is primarily focused on accounting for the impact on the climate change, with 8 and 12 studies addressing the life cycle CO₂ emissions

[42,46,49,57,60,63,69,73] and life cycle GHG emissions [11,40,43,47,51,66,71,74,75,78–80]. The comprehensive LCA analysis is identified in 11 papers, including 2 LCA reviews on H₂ production processes [10,45,48,50,52–56,59,72,84,85]. The detailed analysis of the identified environmental evaluations in terms of technology description, methodology and results is presented in Table 1.

The most widely adopted FU in the selected documents is the mass of H₂ either kg or ton, while the H₂ volume as Nm³ is applied by Dufour et al. [52–55]. Specific FUs are applied when other final products, such as DME [69], MeOH [48], electricity [57], steel [73], and iron mine activity [43] are analysed. Diab et al. [74] define more than one functional unit for their analysis and report the results for all three products obtained: 1 kg H₂, 1 kg carbon black, and 1 kg coke. Salas et al. [11] apply a similar choice, including the FUs of 1 kg of H₂, 1 kg of graphite and 1 MJ of NG feedstock. The adopted system boundaries are cradle-to-gate and gate-to-gate, found 7 [42,45,46,49,57,60,63] and 24 studies [10,11,40,43,47,48,50–56,59,66,69,71–75,78–80], respectively. The gate-to-gate approach is solely on the direct emissions of the process. In contrast, the cradle-to-gate boundaries include the indirect or upstream emissions of feedstocks and electricity. The impact of plant manufacturing is further considered in 12 selected analyses [10,12,45,52–56,72,74,75,79], while Lumbers et al. include the H₂ storage [43] and Al Ghafri et al. [47] the black carbon transport. The Global Warming Potential (GWP) is the most analysed impact indicator. It measures the effect of global warming on the climate change based on the radiative forcing of a unit mass of GHG over a specific time period [97]. The specific characterisation factors for GWP applied in studies are those outlined by the IPCC, as defined in ISO14076.

Other studies adopt the EF [10,51], RECIPE [56,72], and TRACI.

2.1 [48,50,59,71] methods, while in the remaining studies the method applied is not specified [47,66,78,80]. The GWP with 20 years' time horizon is further analysed in Patel et al. [51] and Diab et al. [74]. Beyond GWP, fossil fuel abiotic depletion potential and particulate matter are the most selected impact indicators in the LCA analysis [50,56,72]. A comprehensive approach, including a broader range of environmental indicators, is applied by using the EF [10] and RECIPE 2016 [48,59] and IMPACT 2002+ [45] methods. In Dufour et al. studies [52–54], a single score approach is calculated using the Ecoindicator 95 method [98].

In most environmental analyses, carbon is excluded, and no multi-functional approach is adopted. In the specific cases evaluated by Al Ghafri [47], it is accounted as waste, and its management impact is included. In other scenarios, aligned with the economic evaluation, carbon is accounted for as an added-value byproduct, and the multi-functional approaches, such as system expansion for CB production [10], mass allocation [74,75], energy allocation [11,50] or economic allocation [11,74] are adopted.

Table 2

Carbon market analysis, adapted from Dagle et al. [13].

Carbon form	Price	Market application	Market size	Ref
Carbon black	0.5–2.5 \$/kg	Tyres (90 %), printing inks (9 %), high-performance coatings and plastic, food, water treatment, biochar, and asphalt.	14.5 M MT (2022) 24.0 M MT (2035)	[13,90]
Graphite	0.5–2.7 \$/kg	Pencils, lubricants, foundry facings, polishes, arc lamps, batteries, and fuel cells.	1. 67 M MT (2024)	[13,91,92]
Carbon fiber	20–113 \$/kg	Aerospace, automobiles, sports and leisure, construction, wind turbines, carbon-reinforced composite materials, and textiles.	151 K MT (2023) 415 K MT (2035)	[13,93,94]
Carbon nanotubes	0.1–600 \$/gram	Composite fibres in polymers to improve thermal, electrical, and mechanical properties and possible future for green technologies (battery, solar cell, fuel cell) and water treatment.	3.90 KT (2023)	[13,93,95]
Needle coke	2.5 \$/kg	Graphite electrodes for electric arc steel furnaces	3.20 M MT (2021) 6.70 M MT (2031)	[13,96]

For each document including the cradle-to-gate GHG emissions analysis, the MC base scenario is identified and reported in Table 1. Values are statistically elaborated in Fig. 7. Studies adopting allocation or system expansions as multifunctional approaches are homogenised to allocate all the GHG emissions to the H₂. This choice is adopted to facilitate the comparison between the different studies and to mitigate the uncertainty of the results caused by carbon market variability. The results reported by Salas [11] and Okeke [50] including CCS scenarios are excluded because it was not possible to homogenise the results with the data identified in the study. However, the original and homogenised results are presented in Table 1. When the specific value is not reported from the studies, the value range is extrapolated from the graphics. Studies that report the same process multiple times are included only once. Biomethane as feedstock is not included in the range and will be discussed separately. The Conventional gas GHG emissions range is 1.11–14.5 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂, with median values of 6.10 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂ and Q1 and Q3, respectively, of 3.74 and 6.94 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂. The wide range is due to the process technology (heat supply, CCS integration, efficiency), geographical location (upstream NG and electricity emissions), and NG fugitive emissions accounted. The lowest value was reported by Dufour et al. for a system using a carbonaceous catalyst with an ideal methane conversion rate of 99 % [52,53]. The geographical scope is considered to be an European average [52–55]. The highest value, close to 14.5 kgCO₂eq/kgH₂, was reported by Timmerbergh [12], who accounted for higher CH₄ fugitive emissions of 1.7 % and NG upstream emissions of 17.2 g CO₂eq/MJ. In the Canadian scenario of Alberta, Oni et al. reported GHG emissions of 4.89 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂, which are reduced to 4.54 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂ when CCS is applied [80]. In Okeke et al.'s study, the NG combustion process produces GHG emissions of 7 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂, increasing to 13.6 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂ when CB is combusted. The introduction of CCS technology reduced emissions by 2.4 kg and 4.6 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂, respectively [50].

The MM system's GHG emissions range from 0.78 to 13.2 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂, with median values of 3.91 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂ and Q1 and Q3, respectively, of 2.11 and 7.35 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂. Shokrollahi et al. obtained the lowest value for an MM configuration using H₂ as a heat resource [71]. Postel [72] and Hermesmänn [10] analysed MM methane cracking in the German context, including plant manufacturing and catalyst environmental impacts. Hermesmänn [10] compared to NG, H₂, carbon, and electrical heat supply, the following results were obtained: 6.45, 3.94, 7.65, and 9.91 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂, respectively. The study emphasises the role of the heat supply in determining the technology's

environmental impact, with H₂ burning solutions emerging as the least CO₂ emitting solution. In addition, the analysis is extended by comparing the MC's GHG emissions with SMR CCS and electrolysis for each European country. The GHG emissions range in Europe is reported in Table 1. Kim et al. report the highest GHG emission value of 13.2 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂ [66]. When the carbon capture from the oxyfuel combustor and solid carbon is considered, the GHG emissions drop to −0.31 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂, revealing the technology's carbon removal potential when biomethane is used.

The range of the Plasma system is 1.64–13.5 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂, and it reports broad variation according to the power supply source [12,71]. The actual industrial case of Monolith, powered by renewable energy, is characterised by 4.85 kgCO₂eq/kgH₂ if no allocation is settled. This value changes to 0.91 and 1.16 with economic and mass allocation, respectively [74]. When the power supply is extended to no low carbon emissions supply, the range shifts to 12.5 kgCO₂eq/kgH₂, considering gas combined cycle power plants as an electrical source [12]. While the highest emissions of 13.5 kgCO₂eq/kgH₂ are reached when the reactor is powered by Alberta (Canada) power mix. The GHG emissions of the NTP process are evaluated by Kerscher et al., identifying a range of 1.9–6.4 kgCO₂eq/kgH₂ for renewable and grid German mix energy supply, respectively. The NTP shows the best environmental performance among the Plasma processes due to the lower energy consumption.

The GHG emissions analysis does not highlight any relevant difference within the system processes, which shows a wide range internally according to the heat supply, electricity and NG upstream emissions.

The comprehensive LCA analysis of the MC technologies is limited to conventional gas [45,52–55] and MM systems [10,72]. The comparison of LCA results is difficult considering the different calculation methods applied, which implies different indicators, units of measure and characterisation factors. However, it is possible to identify some indicative specific trends. Besides the GWP category, the use of non-renewable resources, particulate matter and water use are the most investigated midpoint categories. The impact on non-renewable fossil fuel energy is increased compared to the benchmark H₂ technologies [10,45,50,52,55,59,72]. The MC process indeed implies an increased use of NG compared to SMR, due to the stoichiometry of the reaction. In Dufour et al.'s studies, the fossil energy use is analysed and it is lower than SMR CCS. However, in this case, the calculation includes only the use of NG as a combustor, while the use of hydrocarbons as raw materials (e.g., as reactive) for hydrogen production was subtracted [54,55].

Analysing the mineral resource use, Hermesenann et al. [10] and Postels et al. [72] report the highest impact for the MC systems compared to SMR CCS and PEMEL. The increase is related to the presence of molten metal in the reactor. However, the same trend is not observed in Al-Qahtani et al., where the value reported for MM system is higher than SMR and SMR CCS but lower than electrolysis [59]. The discrepancy can be caused by the different system boundaries of the studies. In Al-Qahtani et al., the impact of the manufacturing and infrastructure, including the molten media, is excluded [59]. When considering Conventional Gas and Plasma reactors, none of the identified studies report the impact of these technologies on mineral resource use.

The particulate matter category is analysed by Ali et al. with a gate-to-gate approach, the value obtained is 1 gPM_{2.5}eq./kgH₂ and it is equal to the ones observed for SMR and SMR CCS [45]. A similar value is reported by Okeke et al. with a range of 0.8–1.5 gPM_{2.5}eq./kgH₂ according to the reactor heat system [50]. In Hermesmänn et al. the particulate matter impact increases by 352 % compared to SMR with a value of 1.22e-07 disease incidence/kg H₂ [10]. The discrepancy between the results reported by Hermesmänn et al. [10] and those by Ali et al. [45] and Okeke et al. [50] can be related to the inclusion of the impact of molten metal in Hermesmänn et al.'s studies. However, it is important to note that all identified studies provide an incomplete analysis of particulate matter, as none account for particulate formation during the reaction. This omission could lead to an underestimation of the technology's

Fig. 7. Statistical analysis of cradle-to-gate GHG emissions for the base scenario of Conventional Gas, MM, and Plasma systems as identified in the selected documents and reported in Table 1. All the values included in the statistical analysis are homogenised allocating the emissions to H₂, other multifunctional approaches are excluded.

impact.

Water use is analysed by Hermesmann [10,45], reporting an increase compared to SMR of 249 %, with a value of 5.07e-01 kg world-eq deprived/kg H₂ [10]. In Ali et al. the water use is 5.515 kg/kg H₂ for a gate-to-gate analysis, and lower than SMR and SMR CCS [45]. As previously observed for mineral resource use category, the use of different system boundaries, calculation methods and MC technology lead to different results.

The endpoint categories are analysed by Dufour et al. [52,53] and Al-Qathani et al. [59] for hydrogen and by Mahabir et al. [48] for methanol production, respectively. The endpoint category applied by Dufour et al. [52,53] is the Single Score in Ecoindicator 95 calculation method. The MC shows improved results compared to SMR and SMR CCS, reaching at least 50 % methane conversion efficiency. In Al-Qathani et al. [59] the human health, ecosystem quality and resource depletion categories at the endpoint level are calculated. Consistent with other studies, the resource depletion impact of MC is higher than that of SMR, SMR with CCS, and electrolysis. In terms of Ecosystem Quality and Human Health, MC has a higher impact compared to SMR CCS and electrolysis powered by nuclear or wind energy, but a lower impact than SMR and electrolysis powered by photovoltaic energy.

A holistic LCA analysis including all the impact categories of the selected calculation method is performed by Ali et al. [45], and Hermesmann et al. [10].

Ali et al. [45] performed the LCA analysis of the TCD MC process, accounting for a wide range of midpoint impact indicators covering human health, environment, and cumulative energy demand. The system boundaries are gate-to-gate, excluding the upstream impacts of catalyst and gas extraction. MC reaction showed improved environmental performance compared to SMR CCS in all categories except for the non-renewable energy indicators. Compared to the SMR, the increased impacts are identified in non-renewable energy, aquatic and terrestrial ecotoxicity and ionising radiation indicators. The LCA analysis of MM technology was further developed by Hermesmann et al. [10], comparing it to SMR with and without CCS and electrolysis. In this case, the presence of tin and the higher natural consumption raises the environmental impact of the MC process compared to SMR and SMR CCS processes for all the environmental impact indicators, with the exception of GWP.

The review of LCA analysis in the MC context highlights a lack of methodology homogenization and a scarcity of studies. Specifically, the environmental impact of molten media and catalysts remains unexplored. Similarly, TP and NTP systems are under-researched. Moreover, none of the identified studies evaluate the direct process emissions in terms of particulate matter despite the process involving the direct production of carbon particles. As identified by Hermesmann et al., [10] the increased consumption of natural gas could lead to a higher environmental impact of the MC compared to benchmark H₂ technologies, while the molten metal can have a detrimental effect on the environmental sustainability. However, it is not possible to provide a direct comparison of the MC technologies due to inhomogeneity and scarcity of studies. More efforts should be made in the sustainability research to cover all the environmental indicators, other than GWP, to clearly define the environmental sustainability of the MC process. The selective selection of GWP indicator could indeed favour the MC technologies among the H₂ benchmark process, hiding its detrimental impact on different environmental indicators.

4.3. Social aspects

In the paper review process, any study addressing the analysis of the social impact of MC technologies is identified. The social evaluation represents a new challenge in the scientific community. A first pioneering step was made by Valente comparing the social impact of H₂ production from SMR and biomass gasification in Spain [99]. The analysis evaluates two social indicators: child labour and health

expenditures. Renewable H₂ production processes show reduced impact on child labour indicator, while increased health expenditures due to the higher working hours required per functional unit in countries with non-null social risks. The social assessment of H₂ production via electrolysis in the different configurations (AEL [100], PEMEL [101] and SOEL [102]), has also been analysed. These studies revealed a higher social impact of water electrolysis compared to the SMR due to significant social hotspots in the supply chain of critical equipment [100]. When assessing the social impact of the SMR, significant concerns are related to NG exports [99]. Given the high consumption of NG feedstock in the MC process, the NG supply could significantly influence its social impact. Evaluating the social sustainability of the MC process, alongside environmental and economic factors, is closely tied to the availability of electricity and NG, as well as the geographical location of the plant. Compared to electrolysis, MC technology may have an advantage in social sustainability by avoiding using critical materials required for electrolysers and reactor components. Nevertheless, the social impact of MC technology remains an open question.

4.4. LCOH and GHG emissions comprehensive analysis

The bibliometric analysis reveals that evaluating MC impacts on sustainability pillars predominantly focuses on techno-economic performance and assessing GHG emissions. The reviewed studies report a wide range of LCOH and GHG emissions, influenced by reactor configuration, heat supply, geographical location (including NG and electricity upstream emissions and costs), and carbon selling price. To better understand the economic competitiveness and environmental advantages of each technology in Fig. 8, the MC's cradle-to-gate GHG emissions and LCOH analysis are compared with SMR CCS and electrolysis. Only the reviewed studies, with cradle-to-gate GHG emissions and LCOH analysis, are considered, including the results of Timmerbergh et al. [40], Al Ghafri et al. [47], Okeke et al. [50], Kim et al. [66], Shokrollahi et al. [71], Oni et al. [80], and Kerscher et al. [79]. The values are standardised to allocate all the environmental impact to the H₂. However, a full homogenization of the values according to the calculation method is out of the scope of this study. SMR CCS and electrolysis have been selected as the most promising low carbon emissions hydrogen technologies with highest TRL and deepest diffusion in the market [3]. Their GHG emissions and LCOHs are taken from the IEA report [103].

It is an indicative comparison, considering the different assumptions in each study. A comprehensive comparison should consider the methodological approach and harmonization, which is out of this study's scope.

Analysing the results, the most competitive systems are:

- MM configurations in the British Columbia context. H₂ and electrical heat scenarios yield emissions of 0.8, 1.2 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂ and LCOH of 3.32 and 4.56 \$/kg H₂, respectively [71].
- NTP is powered by renewable energy, with GHG emissions of 1.9 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂ and an LCOH of 2.75 \$/kg H₂ [79].
- TCD with NG combustion in Alberta province, Canada. Among the studies reports the lower LCOH of 1.57 \$/kg H₂, with GHG emissions of 4.9 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂ [80].

The lowest H₂ costs in MC technologies are identified for the TD using NG or carbon as a heat supply. However, this results in high GHG emissions due to fossil fuel combustion. When the NG is applied as fuel, as in the case investigated by Oni et al. in the province of Alberta, the GHG emissions of 4.9 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂ fall in the SMR CCS and electrolysis range [80]. However, when the combustion of the produced carbon is used as heat source, the GHG emissions reach 13.6 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂, surpassing the traditional SMR [50]. Therefore, the potential of MC technologies is highly dependent on the reactor system, geographical location, and carbon revenues. A simultaneous cradle-to-gate GHG emissions analysis and economic analysis are

Fig. 8. Comparison of LCOH and GHG emissions of MC's technologies with SMR CCS and electrolysis. Only the reviewed studies with cradle-to-gate GHG emissions and LCOH analysis are considered, including: Timmerbergh et al. [40], Al Ghafri et al. [47], Okeke et al. [50], Kim et al. [66], Shokrollahi et al., [71], Oni et al. [80], and Kerscher et al. [79]. SMR CCS and electrolysis values are taken from IEA Report [103].

indispensable to show their competitiveness with the SMR CCS and electrolysis clearly.

In the review analysis, a few studies involving the application of biomethane are identified [44,74,75]. In the CF analysis performed by Diab in Monolith's TP system, when biomethane from organic waste is used, and system expansion for carbon byproduct is included and mass allocation applied, H₂ production shows negative emissions equivalent to.

−5.22 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂ [74]. When soybean biomass is applied, and CO₂ land use change is accounted for, the system reaches 0.52 kg CO₂eq/kgH₂, considering mass allocation and including biogenic carbon emissions [75]. The life cycle GHG emissions analysis highlights, on the one hand, the potential of the cracking process as BECCS and, on the other hand, the variability of the results according to the biomass and methodological approach applied. Analysing the process according to the H₂ certification guidelines would be helpful in certifying when the produced H₂ can be defined as sustainable [104]. From the economic point of view, the use of biomethane is analysed by Swartbooi [44]. The LCOH reaches 8.9 \$/kgH₂ with a carbon selling price of 1670 \$/ton. The process is not economically competitive in South Africa, where the system is analysed. Further economic analysis in different contexts would be helpful in defining the process's applicability on a broader scale.

5. Conclusion

This study has provided a comprehensive literature review analysis that have assessed the environmental, economic and social impacts associated to MC technologies, with a total of 46 studies reviewed. MC technologies offer diverse pathways for low-carbon hydrogen production, each with unique advantages and challenges. The scientific research focuses on the Conventional Gas and MM systems, reporting fewer analyses on Plasma technology. The trend contrasts with the industrial scenarios, where Plasma reaches the highest number of high TRL projects.

From an economic perspective, TEA was the predominant method used across studies. LCOH values varied by technology type, with ranges of \$1.1–4.0/kg for Conventional Gas, 0.9–4.6/kg for MM systems, and \$1.8–6.6/kg for Plasma systems. Despite Plasma technologies having higher costs related to electricity consumption, the LCOH values for Conventional Gas and MM systems were comparable. The economic viability of MC was shown to be highly dependent on natural gas and electricity price and carbon revenue, which varied according to carbon product type and market demand.

Regarding environmental aspect, the analysis primarily focused on GHG emissions. The GWP of MC technologies spanned a wide range:

1.1–14.5 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂ for Conventional Gas, 0.8–13.2 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂ for MM systems, and 1.6–12.5 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂ for Plasma systems, considering a cradle-to-gate approach. The variation within and across these categories was primarily driven by the choice of heat supply, upstream emissions from NG, and the electricity mix. When powered by renewable energy or hydrogen, the MC technology exhibited lower GHG emissions compared to SMR CCS or electrolysis. On the other hand, the use of gas and or carbon as heat supply involves higher emissions but remains competitive in terms of cost. Understanding these dynamics is critical when selecting hydrogen production technologies based on both economic and environmental goals.

The social impact of MC technologies, however, remains significantly underexplored. No studies in this review provided an SLCA of MC. Given the importance of natural gas in the MC process and the geographical variability in NG supply chains, future studies should address the potential social impacts, such as labor conditions, local community effects, and the sector's contribution to economic development.

Looking ahead, several research gaps need to be addressed to comprehensively assess the sustainability of MC technologies:

- 1. Harmonization of methodologies:** There is a need for more standardized approaches to techno-economic and life cycle assessments, especially in terms of system boundaries, functional units, multi-functional approach, and calculation method.
- 2. Environmental performance:** GHG emissions from MC processes range from 0.8 to 14 kg CO₂eq/kg H₂, highlighting the technology's potential for low-carbon hydrogen production. However, this wide range underscores the need for optimized process configurations and careful consideration of energy sources.
- 3. High-TRL Plasma systems:** Future research focused on sustainability should align with the technological advancements in these areas.
- 4. Social impact assessments:** Future studies should prioritize S-LCA to evaluate the social implications of MC technologies, particularly in regions where natural gas supply chains pose significant socio-economic risks.
- 5. Biomethane as a feedstock:** The use of biomethane in MC offers a promising pathway for negative emissions, but further research is needed to assess its economic competitiveness and sustainability.
- 6. Research Gaps:** Significant knowledge gaps persist, particularly the analyses of particulate matter formation in MC processes and environmental impacts of molten media.
- 7. Carbon Valorization:** The economic feasibility of MC technologies is closely tied to the development of markets for the solid carbon

byproduct. Further research into high-value carbon applications could significantly enhance the overall viability of MC processes.

8. **Geographical Considerations:** The performance of MC technologies varies significantly based on location, emphasizing the importance of region-specific assessments that account for local energy mixes and regulatory environments.

Lastly, it can be said that among the reviewed technologies, Non Thermal Plasma (NTP) systems powered by renewable energy stand out as one of the most promising option due to their lower energy consumption and the absence of catalytic materials that could compromise environmental performance. Future research should focus on further evaluating the environmental, economic, and social performance of innovative NTP MC technologies, enhancing the understanding of their role in sustainable hydrogen production.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Isabella Bulfaro: Investigation, Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Anna Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing. **Gabriela Benveniste:** Writing – review & editing. **Beatriz Amante García:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Víctor José Ferreira:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization, Methodology.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Copilot in order to improve the text readability and work language. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of competing interest

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